

WOMEN AS AGENTS OF PEACEBUILDING IN IGBO CULTURE

Ronald Olufemi Badru *PhD.*

Department of Politics and International Relations,
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Badru.ronald@lcu.edu.ng

&

Lilian N. Akhanolu,

Department of Peace Studies and Conflict Resolution,
Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo, Oyo State, Nigeria.

akhanolulilian@gmail.com

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14767833>

Abstract

Igbo women are agents of peacebuilding. The Igbo culture empowers them to be an Integral part of conflict resolution in Igbo world where the men appear to be the central focus. In this article, women have been seen as agents in both proactive and reactive peacebuilding. Three communities in the southeast were used as case studies. They include, Umuahia in Abia State, Mbano in Imo State and Ozubulu in Anambra State. Through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, the researchers found out that in line with Akachi Adimora Ezeigbo's *Snail-sense feminism theory* which is the foundation of this study, the respondents from the study areas have proved to us that women are indeed peacebuilders. The voices of the respondents have shown that in Igbo nation, women are invaluable when it comes to finding peace and sustaining it. This study recommends that women living in the communities be given the opportunity to advise those in authority on how peace can be managed in Igboland; that women themselves should form a league of women in Igbo land to serve as an instrument for

getting their voices heard in the region; that women be made agents of peace by giving them more support in the politics of the region; that women should believe in themselves and fight for their rights in the communities they find themselves.

Keywords: Igbo women; agents of peacebuilding; Conflict resolution; Igbo Culture; southeast.

Introduction

Conflict is universal. It occurs every second, minute, hour, day, week, month. In fact, conflicts live with us just as we live with conflicts. It can be found in homes, Churches, Mosques, schools, in one organization or the other locally and internationally.

Conflict is ambiguous as a term and does not have a comprehensive universal definition (Aluko, 2014). What this implies is the fact that what could trigger conflict in one community may not do so in another community. Conflicts are in two broad perspectives – the overt and covert: ‘The overt forms of conflict are the ones we experience every day in the form of absenteeism, sabotage, go-slow, work-to-rule, restriction of output, non-cooperation and industrial action such as strike actions, lockouts and boycotts. The covert forms are complacency, sabotage, stealing, no-productivity and low dedication to duty, which characterise the workplace in the modern world’ (Akanji, 2018). The study falls in the second category, covert since community conflicts are involved and a good number of times involve family issues that may include stealing, usurpation and fighting. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2022) observed that “in a society or community filled with hatred, people begin to feel suffocated and depressed, as discrimination makes miserable lives for not just those discriminated against, but everyone in the society”.

There are six types of conflicts. They include *intra-personal conflict* which deals with a person’s problems, how to manage his time, finance, who to marry and what course to study. The second type is *inter-personal*, conflicts between friends,

colleagues and family members. The third is *intra-group conflict*, which is about conflicts within a group, fourth is *inter-group conflicts*, which has to do with conflicts between two groups. The fifth and sixth are *intra-national and international conflicts* respectively.

For Achebe, the Igbo is a nation and not a tribe (Achebe, 2009). In his words, ‘...Igbo people might score poorly on the Oxford dictionary test for tribe...Now, to call them a nation...This may not be perfect for the Igbo, but it is close.’ On this rather cautious tone and notion by the scholar on what the Igbos are, one has a clear idea of the Igbo as a nation. Igbo language is the mother tongue of the five South-Eastern states of Nigeria (Emenanjo, et al, 2011). These states are: Anambra, Abia, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo. Igbo language is also spoken in parts of Delta, Rivers, Edo, Benue, Cross River and Akwa Ibom States. It is spoken as first or second language by at least, 35 million people (Emenanjo, et al, 2011). With these statistics, the Igbo world is a big nation with a large population that demand better economy for sustenance and may as a result, take to migration towards improving themselves.

It has been argued that ‘Peacebuilding is aimed at putting in place the social, economic, political and environmental mechanisms necessary for making lasting peace possible. It is not a question of constructing make-shift or temporary shelter...’ Peacebuilding can be pre-conflict or post conflict (Albert, 2001). The former tries to prevent a conflict from breaking out, while the latter is reactive and includes reconstruction of social infrastructure, the rehabilitation of displaced persons and reconciliation or mutual cooperation’ (Albert, 2001). In addition, Albert stated that ‘peacebuilding is essentially non-coercive and comprises all efforts necessary to make the environment conducive for peace to reign’ (2001).

With regards to the above submissions, peacebuilding by the Igbo women is a culture that has been with the women for a

long time. It is on this basis that the Igbo women, home and abroad, always hold meetings for the development of their communities. These women are so organized that they erect commendable edifices in their communities. Oaikhena, (2022) rightly noted that “human conduct is necessary in peace building”.

Recently, there is a new development among the Igbo women living abroad. They travel to home communities to brainstorm with their women counterparts on ways to move the communities forward. This has become what is today known as ‘August Meeting’. Applying this strategy has become almost compulsory that every Igbo woman living outside their husbands’ home communities must travel home. In some, communities, any woman who fails to do so and without a good reason is meant to pay a huge fine. According to Idehen and Oaikhena (2021) they argued that “strategy formulation is recognized as both an art and science. Strategies, are often linked to individuals’ personalities in the eye of the public, and some individuals appear to have a particular talent for this art and science”. During these annual visits, a lot is done by women. It has become a healthy competition among women of different communities in the eastern states to come up with one project or another and getting such executed in good time. These projects included schools for girls, clinics, halls for their meetings, which could be rented to generate money, and so many other projects meant to aid their husbands’ efforts towards community building. According to Oaikhena and Ajagun, (2015) “...infrastructural development leads to a peaceful and harmonious and just society where the people have a sense of strong community identity and belonging, that is truly valued by the state, and is adequately empowered and motivated to contribute to the task of nation building”. All these were geared to accommodate those who are migrating from other climes.

Human Migration from one location to another has been the concern of International Organisation for Migration (IOM)

since 1951 when it was established. As an inter-governmental organisation, it looks at the fate and wellbeing of migrants across the globe. The Igbo nation, one of the three major ethnic groups in Nigeria are industrious and business-oriented set of people, who compete with one another for economic buoyance. One of the platforms for competition is on migrating to the outside world other than the Igbo homeland, for further studies and economic activities. The migrants remit money to their relatives to invest at home and take care of their social and economic needs.

In the early nineteen eighties in the old *Imo Broadcasting Service* (the then only radio station in the old Imo State now divided into Imo and Abia States in Nigeria), there was a very popular programme. It was called *Oje mba*. The programme entails a certain traveller from a particular part of Igbo land who moved from one community to the other in search of greener pastures. That unique programme was a brilliant platform for different cultures of the peoples of the Igbo world to be showcased. Each week, *Ojemba* (the persona who anchor the programme) metaphorically is called *Ojemba 'The traveller'* is found in a new community. He normally has a good rapport with his hosts but will eventually commit a cultural taboo which he will be made to appease the land after his struggles and arguments that he has done nothing bad. This could be the reason why Oaikhena and Osawe (2012), posits that “losers are safe in the knowledge that they will neither lose their lives nor their liberty, and will continue to participate in public life”.

Migrating from Igbo communities to other places for economic reasons is common to the Igbo men and women. The Igbos mix well with their hosts. They are known for identifying with each other through monthly meetings where they discuss issues that affect their ancestral homes and, in these meetings, they help in peacebuilding by sending money home to solve one problem or the other. Women do so too. A good example being the just alluded '*August meeting*'.

Migration in Igbo land is a culture. The Igbo leave their villages and go and live in another which may be very near (in fact, a neighbouring one) for the simple reason of engaging in a new venture they will not ordinarily achieve in their own villages. In other words, migration to the Igbo man is life. The Igbo man travels around in order to become much richer and come back home as a better man for his people to respect and love. *Ojemba enwegh iro* ‘A traveller or a migrant does not have any enemy’ is therefore, a cultural coinage which encourages the Igbos to migrate for positive empowerment but to be mindful of the culture of his hosts. The concept is didactic in the sense that it does not encourage any Igbo migrant to go and break his hosts’ customs and traditions; rather, it teaches the morality that the visitor and his host must live in peace and that the peacefulness must be planted by the migrant. Put differently, *Ojemba enweghi iro* is a paradox which reminds the migrant that though you may face enemies in the course of your migration and stay, notwithstanding, all effort must be made not to allow conflict to arise and when it does arise, the migrant is reminded to be the one to seek quick resolution just as the Radio Programme *Ojemba* alluded ever did.

Aims and objectives of the study

The primary aim of this study is to assess the involvement of women in peacebuilding in Southeast of Nigeria. The research focused on four objectives:

- i. to assess the nature of conflict resolution done by women in southeast Nigeria;
- ii. to investigate women’s involvement in conflict resolution in Southeast Nigeria;
- iii. to find out the kind of peacebuilding: proactive or reactive, women engage in;
- iv. to see women as agents of peacebuilding.

In view of these the significance of the study was to ascertain the involvement of women in peacebuilding in the eastern part of Nigeria. This is against the belief that the women are weak and not recognized in Igbo land. In this context, the research focuses on married women in Igboland and the way they manage peace in their communities.

The study covered three communities in Igbo land, these are: Anambra, Imo, and Abia States. The specific communities were, Ozubulu in Anambra, Mbano in Imo and Umuahia in Abia. The three states have been chosen because of their proximities to each other.

Definitions of terms

Women: Women in Igbo culture are those who are married from one family or community to another. A woman not married cannot inherit anything from her father. In other words, what constitutes a female being called 'woman' is marriage to a man. This status gives her the right to belong to social gatherings and women meetings, which gives her a sense of belonging and the authority to contribute in matters concerning women in the community.

Conflict: This is a clash of interest between one person or group of persons. Conflict is inevitable to man and can have a positive benefit if well managed. In other words, conflict is not entirely negative as many people think. Conflict can be seen as the opposite of peace because if conflict is properly managed, it is aimed at achieving sustainable peace with justice and fairness.

Peacebuilding: This is a kind of peace resolution which helps to forestall conflict taking place at all, or when conflict has already taken place, peacebuilding attempts to mend issues and bring peace back to the community. In other words, peacebuilding is a mechanism to bridge peace between people or groups of people.

Sometimes, it may be between warring states of factions. The concept of peacebuilding was made popular in 1992 at the United Nations (UN).

Southeast: This is one of the six geopolitical zones that make up Nigeria. This region comprises the Igbos in Anambra, Enugu, Ebonyi, Imo, and Abia states.

Methodology

A qualitative research method was adopted, using ethnographic research design. This is in order to directly deal with people's experience, feeling and interpretations in the situations they find themselves. Primary and secondary data were used. For primary data, in-depth interview and focus group discussion (FGD) were used. The interviews were conducted in Igbo language. For the secondary data, the researcher depended on books and other printed materials.

Focus Group Discussions

Focus group discussion conducted in umuahia on 28 February, 2024

In Umuahia's focus group discussion at Okwu Community Hall, Olokoro, the eight voices reiterated what had earlier been said by their fellow women in the In-depth interviews. All the voices concurred that women in Umuahia focus on matters that affect women and the entire land and that they do so with the cooperation of their husbands.

a. *Research Question 1: What is the nature of conflict resolution done by women in southeast Nigeria?*

Responses: Mrs Ekwutosi Nwankwo: We look into conflicts that affect women and we go for justice. We do not look at faces but maintain standard as we are mindful of posterity. We do not take bribes but ensure that the guilty person is brought to book so that, examples would be set for others to follow.

Mrs Ihuoma Emereuwa: You are right, Ekwy. To add to what you have said, women do not select the type of cases to look into. We discuss issues concerning married women, our girl child and boy child, and even our husbands. I will say that the only two kinds of conflicts we do not look into are issues that relate to murder which the police have the right to investigate on behalf of the state, on one hand, and on the other, technical or spiritual matters reserved for only men alone to resolved. For instance, it is the men alone who can resolve boundaries of lands for parties in conflict. They have their special way of doing so.

b. *Research Question 2: How do women get involved in conflict resolution in the southeast Nigeria?*

Responses: **Mrs Lois Ejim:** There is no single way we get involved. It is natural that we get involved when consulted by the parties in conflict. When they come to women for help in resolving the conflict before them, we thank them for believing in us and then set a day to look into their matters in our village hall.

Mrs Ekwutosi Nwankwo: To add to what my fellow woman has said, women do not actually wait till they are consulted. If it is a very serious case, women are attracted by the noise or shouts of fights and step in immediately. In other words, we are ever ready to intervene in conflicts in the land whether invited or not.

Mrs Ihuoma Emereuwa: We also act on rumours. When there has been a consistent rumour that some serious conflict has been brewing in the neighbourhood, women begin to investigate with the intention to bring whoever is culpable to his or her senses. We believe that there is no fire without smoke. So, some rumours are indicators that we women should stand up to protect the community. In Umuahia, women are soldiers. We protect our

environment physically, mentally, and even spiritually by organizing occasional prayers in our halls where every woman is mandated to attend.

- c. *Research Question 3: Which kinds of peacebuilding do women engage in: proactive or reactive?*

Responses: **Mrs Ihuoma Gbaruko:** We engage in both proactive and reactive peacebuilding. Our proactive peacebuilding is inbuilt in our rules and regulations where we specify the punishment that will be meted out on any person, who goes against the laws of the land. For reactive peacebuilding, we deal with them when the need arises. For example, recently, a woman here in Okwu stole a grandchild and women deliberated on the issue till the woman was sent away from the village. Women do not rush things. We take our time to investigate and then act collectively. We keep our secrets so that our plans do not leak.

Mrs Cecilia Obinna: Let me add another example of reactive peacebuilding done by us women. A woman recently took knife and stabbed his landlord here in Umuahia. Women took it up upon themselves and marched to the place and ensured that the woman was locked up by the police. And when the woman was released after settling her case with the police, we, the women agreed that the woman must leave the community, and it was so. Our men supported us because they knew we were protecting their interests too. The woman in question does not hail from Olokoru, but from another clan of Umuahia.

- d. *Research Question 4: Are women seen as agents of peacebuilding?*

Responses: **Mrs Ihuoma Emereuwa:** Absolutely yes, we are. Let me give you an example, when there is a big problem in the land and women cannot handle it and the

issue is about a woman or women, there is an instrument here called Okonko Cult. Whenever, this Okonko steps in and uses its 'gong' to call for calmness, nobody talks again. It is after this that the conflict can now be looked into by the men with women's participation. What I am trying to say is that women in Umuahia are peace loving and we practise peace because it has no alternative. We support every instrument that can be used to have peace in our community, like the Okonko cult. In our social aspect, it is the best way to resolve issues pertaining to land. So, we women can also consult them to help us resolve boundary disputes. You cannot do such if you are not an agent of peace. Even though women do not belong to the cult, we believe in them and obey their verdicts for peace to reign in our land.

Mrs Ekwutosi Nwankwo: To further assert that women are agents of peace in Umuahia, let me give you this instance. There was a woman who stole N300,000.00 from another woman. The owner reported the theft to us and we women swiftly stepped in and made deep investigations after which it was discovered that the accused woman really stole the money. The accused woman was made to pay the money and was heavily punished in such a way to serve as deterrent to others.

Mrs Lois Ejim: In Umuahia, when a person, be it a male or female goes to the farm to harvest cassava or firewood on a wrong day, women accost such person and collect fine. It is our responsibility to protect the farm products from being stolen.

Mrs Adanne Ukandu: We have good rapport with our women in our effort to make peace in the community. Our men from time to time, support us with money and personally buy us ingredients to enable us entertain

ourselves for all the good work we do to support them in achieving peace in the community.

Mrs Enyioma Ejenma: In Umuahia, every village has a special day they sweep or weed their environments. If a woman fails to come out for such without good reasons, such a woman is heavily fined. This is because, women see cleanliness as a very important part of living. They see any woman no matter how well placed who does not come out for cleanings as an enemy of the land. So, women are agents of peace because peace entails cleanliness and orderliness. I believe we women, have all these two virtues and they have been very helpful in keeping peace in our community.

Focus Group Discussion Conducted in Ozubulu on 2nd April, 2024

Describe the nature of conflict resolution carried by women in southeast Nigeria?

Responses: Mrs Ikiru Eze-ego responded that women engagement in conflict resolution mainly revolves around infidelity in the home. She expressed the diverse lasting negative effects the indulgence of this singular act has caused families of perpetrators. Mrs Chidera Mba, said that the women of Ozubulu frowns at theft and heavily fine any woman caught in the act of stealing either in the market or farm. In addition, Mrs Njideka Ozumba concurred to the earlier submissions and further highlighted that their involvements extend to women condemning those engaged in fights with fellow women or even with the men in the community. Mrs Ozumba added that it is tantamount to a taboo for a woman to expose her body in the cause of fighting. In fact, she said that women in Ozubulu see any woman that fights in public as not being responsible.

How do women get involved in conflict resolution the southeast Nigeria?

On the part of Mrs Chiemerie Nwani, she revealed that women of Ozubulu get involved through creating a forum where both women living outside the community and those at home fix a special meeting called, “*August Meeting*”. According to her, this peculiar gathering affords the women to engage in addressing series of conflict for the progress of the entire community.

She also said that, on other occasions, women who in one time or the other had issues to settle, invite the women privately or publicly either by going to the executives or presenting it to the general Women Association, to look into their matter. In view of this, such matters are resolved under the women organization.

In her analysis on how women get involved in conflict resolution, Mrs Felicia Tochukwu said that, their women organization in Ozubulu is formidable. Because of the women’s track records over the years in Ozubulu, Mrs Tochukwu said that their men have supported the women by allowing them to anchor some peacebuilding exercises in the community.

Mrs Dorothy Emezue explained that women easily observe things and know when the community is having conflicts issues. Without being invited, women go into investigation so as to prevent conflict from taking place. She also said that the women are also consulted by parties for a quick settlement.

What kind of peacebuilding do women engage in: proactive or reactive?

In reacting to this question, Mrs Udoka Chukwuka explained one of the measures women take for proactive peacebuilding. She said, that to ensure the effectiveness of women engaging in proactive peacebuilding, messages of peace and peace talks are constantly organized for women during their gatherings. In this special sessions, women of advanced age who had lots of experiences and who are known for their good characters, speak

to the younger women who in turn, take these pieces of advice on how to live in peace within the community and their respective homes.

Mrs Ugonma Mbachu in her contribution added that women make sure that when an individual or group are engaged in destructive conflict, the women as a body usually see it as a necessity to build. Mrs Mbachu also sees women as playing the role of reactive peacebuilding because she said that when conflict has occurred, women do all they can to bring peace back to the community.

Are women seen as agents of peacebuilding?

Mrs Udoka Chukwuka said that women are seen as agents of peacebuilding, because men are fully in support of them and even invite them from time to time for combined meetings where they brainstorm for the upliftment and progress of the community, socially and economically.

Mrs Chiemerie Nwani also was of the opinion that women are agents of peacebuilding. She gave an instance where the men alongside with the women jointly rescued a situation of married couples who fought, wounded themselves and threatened to go on their different paths. But with the intervention of women, the couples were reconciled and today these couples are still together thereby making their families a more peaceful one.

Focus Group Discussion Conducted in Mbano on 28th March, 2024

The following responses were got from focus group discussion conducted in Mbano.

What is the nature of conflict resolution done by women in southeast Nigeria?

Mrs Chidinma Okorie in her response, said that women look into conflicts that concern husbands and wives, theft in the community. This Mrs Patience Nwachukwu supported saying that women

should not leave their marriages in times of trials, but support their husbands. In the words of Mrs Adaoma Nwosu she said that, 'Women make sure, theft issues are not treated with levity. Rather, proper punishment should be meted out to any culprit.' For Mrs Geoginia Agugum, she said that women frown at women who engage in infidelity and that women ensure that such women are dealt with since they bring shame to womanhood. Mrs Aguagaum also condemned women fighting in public and concluded that such was a taboo and whoever is caught in such act is disciplined and fined by the women of Mbano.

How do women get involved in conflict resolution in the southeast Nigeria?

According Mrs Njideka Ikeneri, in southeast Nigeria, especially in this part of Mbano, we get involved mainly when a matter is brought to our notice through our woman leader. The woman leader who of course is the mouthpiece of women makes arrangements to gather the womenfolk so that she could intimate them with the complaints brought before her. Another woman, Mrs Florence Nwakanma concurred to this submission, stating that when the leader receives such matter, since she is not an island, she will invite the public relation officer (PRO) and gives her directives of appropriate time to utilize the local drum (ekere) to gather the entire women of the community, to discuss the issues reported. Mrs Patience Nwachukwu added that the women get involved in conflict resolution in the southeast of Nigeria when they sense that there is abnormality going on in the community that showcases the environment or community as *sitting on a gunpower that might soon explode*.

What kind of peacebuilding do women engage in: proactive or reactive?

Response: Mrs Patience Nwachukwu said that women quickly fling into action for peacebuilding, which is proactive so as to

arrest the situation and prevent any destructive occurrence when a report is given to them over an impending conflict.

While Mrs Chika Duru explained that women engage in peacebuilding in the community by pointing out certain vices women should not engage in. At this juncture, Mrs Adaoma Nwosu cut her off gently and mentioned the following as the vices. These include: fighting in public places, husband snatching, wife/husband maltreatment, theft, and pre-marital pregnancies by the young girls in the community.

Mrs Chidinma Okorie said that they engage in peace talks in the community whenever problem has not emerged as well as when it has erupted. In her analysis, the essence of their peacebuilding is to in-still in the mentality of individuals the *dos* and *don'ts* of the community. In her words concerning reactive peacebuilding, she said, whenever someone has committed an offence, they ensure that the women converge to look into the issues. For instance, the woman who maltreated her husband to a point she refused to join him to relocate to his community, when their economic strength could not carry them, but to continue living in Lagos. As the man relocate to the village all alone, at a point he became very sick. The villagers noticing this were not comfortable so that the women went into action and mandated the woman in Lagos to come back home and take care of her husband.

The woman according to Mrs Okorie and supported by others, said that the threat to the women worked as the woman came back from Lagos. She however did not stay in the village but took the man, her husband to Lagos saying that she would not leave her business. Eventually, the man died in Lagos due to lack of care. When the corpse was brought home, the women were furious against the fellow woman and heavily fined her for not taking good care of her husband.

Are women seen as agents of peacebuilding?

Mrs Patience Nwachukwu sees women as agents of peacebuilding. In her opinion, women forum is an appendage of the men's forum. Therefore, men always give directives to handle certain matters when they sense danger in the community. According to Mrs Nwachukwu, men know that there are conflicts women handle much better than the men. She therefore, concluded that women are agents of peacebuilding and that they work hand in hand with their husbands.

On the part of Mrs Eucharia Uzoma, her answer was in the affirmative, that is, women are indeed agents of peacebuilding in southeast of Nigeria. She said that women in her community are highly respected because of critical issues they had handled in the past. For instance, women were at the forefront of returning a new born baby who was stolen from the community, they ensured that the stolen and sold baby was returned from the motherless babies' home outside Mbano community. Mrs Njideka Ikeneri expressed her profound gratitude to the women and said that the way women handled the issue was so much appreciated by the state government at that particular time and of course, their husbands and community.

Mrs Chika Duru, said she believes that women are agents of peacebuilding in Mbano because they have limited the excesses of women abandoning their husbands, vice versa. Mrs Florence Nwakanma in her opinion, said that women have without reservation, been noted as agents of peacebuilding as they have helped in bringing back couples who had one time or the other, separated from each other.

Findings

In line with Akachi Adimora Ezeigbo's *Snail-sense feminism theory* which is the foundation of this study, the respondents from the study areas of Umuahia, Mbano and Ozubulu, proved that women are indeed peacebuilders. The respondents shown that in Igbo land, women are invaluable when it comes to finding peace

and sustaining it. It is important to note that, women from what we got from the field are a cultural instrument in managing conflict and ensuring that peace reigns in the communities.

The women of Igbo land from what this study gathered are hardworking and they also work with their male counterpart as collaborators in peace matters. The women are not seen as second-class citizens when it comes to the management of conflicts in their communities. This is evident in the instances given by the respondents and from literatures.

Conclusion

The study has established that Igbo women are peacebuilders and agents of peace. The culture of Igbo permits this because the Igbo culture sees women as home keepers and the eyes that watches over the children. These days, one hears of *Women August* meetings in all parts of Igbo land. This is a new innovation that was not operational years back. During these *August meetings*, women abroad return home and brainstorm with their female counterparts residing at home. It is during these meetings that conflicts, and other issues are resolved amicably, and funds realized are deployed for developmental purposes of the communities. Any woman that fails to attend the *August meeting* without cogent reasons is fined heavily. Finally, the study revealed that what men can do, women can as well do. This is in positive perspective as the study clearly has found out that a women's strength in peacebuilding – *proactive and reactive* is commendable. This is because, they produce positive results which in turn, translate to peace, the crux of the matter.

Recommendations

This study recommended as follows:

- a. that
women living in the communities should be given opportunities to advise those in authority on how peace can be managed in Igbo land. At present, women do not have a voice in what goes on in the east, especially as it concerns the separatist movement of IPOP which makes lives very difficult in the eastern part of Nigeria.
- b. that
women themselves should form a league of women in Igbo land to serve as an instrument for getting their voices heard in the region. This gathering of local women will help bring sustainable peace to the region because women, like the snail are very patient and when they come up with resolutions on issues, such have also been based on objectivity.
- c. that
women be made agents of peace by giving them more support in the politics of the region. This can be achieved by the region giving some percentage of slots to women from the state Houses of Assembly. This will greatly trigger more participation of women in politics and consequently showcase them to peacebuilding at the state level instead of being village and clans' champions alone.
- d. that
women should believe in themselves and fight for their rights in the communities they find themselves. They do not need to do this by competing with their men. They can rise and be recognized than what they are at present, by pushing the more for girl education. This is the solution for the future to political empowerment of women.

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FEDERAL CHARACTER PRINCIPLES: ITS IMPACT AND CHALLENGES IN NIGERIA

Lemon Blessing Ebenezer

College of Management and Social Sciences
Glorious Vision University Ogwa,
Edo State Nigeria

lemonisblessed@gmail.com 08065824273

&

Oaikhena I. Marvellous

College of Management and Social Sciences
Glorious Vision University Ogwa,
Edo State, Nigeria.

Abstract

Studies revealed that no nation can attain development for the enhancement of the living standards of the people without a public service that is well organized to implement government policies. As a result, federal character principles in Nigeria represents equitable representation of individuals in the civil service and prevent the dominance of persons from a few states or ethnic groups in the workplace or political governance Nigeria. The principle is often poorly implemented in Nigeria as enshrined in the constitution, making enforcement difficult and the commission tasked with enforcing the principles lacks the power to impose sanctions or violation. With regard to these, the paper examined federal character principles, impact and challenges in Nigeria public service. With the adoption and analysis of secondary method of data

generation, the study observed that the implementation of the federal character principle in Nigerian public service tends to encourage unethical behaviour amongst public officials as it circumscribes merit in the area of manpower procurement and promotion. The study concludes that for Nigerian public service to achieve its mandate of facilitating development, there is need for the government to reappraise the implementation of the federal character principles through the enforcement of merit, anchored on public service reform initiatives that can galvanize human capacity and governmental institutions for sustainable development.

Keywords: Federal character principle, administrative effectiveness, development, public service

Introduction

The Federal Character Principle in Nigeria aims to ensure equitable representation in public service, promoting integration, national unity, and reducing ethnic dominance. The principle was introduced in the 1979 Constitution, it mandates that government appointments should reflect Nigeria's diverse demographics. However, its implementation has faced criticisms for fostering nepotism and inefficiency, as recruitment often prioritizes ethnic affiliation over merit. This has led to increased ethno-regional tensions and questions about administrative effectiveness, complicating nation-building efforts. Despite its intentions, the principle has sometimes exacerbated divisions rather than mitigate them. Plural and sharply divided societies all over the world attempt to manage their diversities and divisive tendencies through one or combination of policy alternatives in the organization and management of their public services for performance; and Nigeria is not an exception (Ayoade, 2000; Abdullah, 2007). Often times, these policy alternatives turn out to be delicate arrangements; but when carefully conceived, crafted and practiced, it provides opportunity for center-seeking and center-fleeing forces to interact peacefully and co-habit on agreed terms. One of such policy alternatives adopted for the management of the public service in Nigeria for even representation is the federal character principle, which "was borne

out of the need to ensure even spread of government appointment, in all the regions, states and local government councils in the country" (Nzeshi, 2012). This could be the reason why Oaikhena and Bendrix (2023) advocated for policies that are redistributive, as they posit that "policies that are redistributive in nature have become essential components, which are strategically used for the reduction of inequality and promotion of sustainable development in the society".

Nigeria is a federal society comprising 36 states structure, with a population of more than 150 million people and has more than 250 ethnic groups, which necessitate an arrangement that could accommodate people from the different segments of the country in the public bureaucracy (Gberevbie, 2012). The notion of federal character presupposes the existence of a federal society. However, as a federal state, Nigeria was faced with the challenge of how to imbibe the principle of federalism in practice. As a result, the quota system was introduced into the Nigerian public service in 1958 by the government "to ensure equitable representation of the various groups in the country" (Tonwe and Oghator, 2009). To further consolidate on the gains of the quota system, the Federal Military Government of Generals Murtala Mohammed and Olusegun Obasanjo in the drafting and approval of the 1979 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria during the transition to civilian rule (1976-79) introduced into the Nigerian political and administrative landscapes the principle of federal character.

Federal character principle sought to give "opportunities in education and employment, usually at the point of entry, to disadvantaged groups and areas to enable them compete and catch up with more advanced areas and sectors of the nation". In comparing the practice of quota system with that of the federal character principle, the latter demands (far more) than the former in the sense that "it switches emphasis from opportunities to privileges and benefits." It was argued that federal character

principle is a legal weapon put in place to regulate appointments, promotions, security of tenure and severance in every government department. The reference to the phrase "disadvantaged groups" in the area of educational opportunities means that "special consideration should be given to candidates from the Northern provinces and other areas where educational facilities were more backward than elsewhere". The awkward application of the federal character principle tends to pose challenges to administrative effectiveness in the Nigerian public service through the circumscription of merit. Such practice of the principle of federal character in personnel procurement without due regard for merit is more likely to mire efforts at sustainable development in a society.

The formal adoption of the federal system in Nigeria, which came into existence with the introduction of the Littleton constitution of 1954, signaled the need for representative bureaucracy that could address the problem in the composition of the federal public service anchored on effective service delivery (Ayoade, 2000; Ikelegbe, 2004). Public service or administrative effectiveness requires a blend of theory with practice. Accordingly, Max Weber (1864-1920), showed the way forward on how to achieve organizational effectiveness through the theory of ideal bureaucracy; and it is doubtful if any modern human organization, whether in public and private sector can function adequately without adhering to the principle of rationality in employee procurement and rewards as postulated by Max Weber (Anyebe, 2004).

The features of the Weberian (legal-rational) model are: hierarchy which implies structure; promotion based on professional merit; skills as guide for recruitment; the development of career service; reliance on and use of rules and regulations that are scientific; impersonality of relationships among career professionals and their clientele in the bureaucracy, specialization along functional lines; authority and responsibility;

and proper documentation or record-keeping in a formal organizational or nation (Anyebe, 2004; Henry,2007).

Arising from the above, the questions that come to mind are: how has the public service adapted to the Weber's bureaucratic model of rational legal authority for administrative effectiveness in Nigeria? As a federal state, how has the principle of federal character in the procurement and promotion of employees helped to bring into the public service the required competent workforce for enhanced performance? What are the merits and demerits of the introduction and the current implementation of the federal character principle in the Nigerian public service for sustainable development? These questions underline the authors attempt at interrogating the utility and viability of the application of federal character principle in the nation's quest for achieving administrative effectiveness for sustainable development. The study is limited to Federal character principles in Nigeria, impact and challenges. It focuses on the Federal civil service from 2019-2024.

Problems associated with federal character principles in Nigeria

The adoption of Federal character in principles in Nigeria was aimed at addressing the problems of marginalization and inequality in governance and appointment into civil service. The idea was good, however, it failed to yield desired results as major ethnic groups keep dominating political positions in the country including the civil service. Poor implementation of the policy due to manipulation and exclusion of the minority from federal civil service. This research is undertaken with a view of addressing these mirages of problems. The research thus became significant because it would enable members of the public to understand the challenges and impact of implementing federal character principles in Nigeria, and would also enable policy makers to make informed decisions that would ensure strict

implementation of Federal character principles. Moreso it would serve as a source of materials for those who might want to embark on similar study.

Literature Review

Federal character and administrative effectiveness in the Nigerian public service

The federal character principle which made its debut in-to the Nigerian political and public administrative landscape through the drafting and adoption of the 1979 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria appeared to be a normative expression of the historical belief of Nigerians in equal access to and participation in the political and administrative affairs of the country in the area of policy formulation and implementation. To support the above view, Alubo (2003) point out that the lack of representation in policy making and implementation by some segments of the Nigerian society in the past has denied them the opportunities for education and economic advancement. Oaikhena (2023) observed that “public policy occurs when individuals or groups respond to real or perceived environmental conditions”.

In order to drive the implementation of the federal character principle, the Federal Character Commission (FCC) was established by decree 34 of 1996, and the powers of the commission was summarized by Mustapha (2007) to include: working out formula for sharing posts and services; compliance monitoring; enforcement of compliance through legal actions; demanding and reviewing data on staffing; and institutional investigations. The FCC is a commission under the presidency, its members are appointed by the president, but subject to the ratification of the Nigerian Senate. To ensure equity in representation, the law establishing the commission states that, the executive chairman and secretary are to be appointed in such a way that if the chairman comes from the North, the secretary

must be chosen from the South and vice versa. However, Nzeshi (2012) argues that "since its establishment, the Federal Character Commission has been headed mostly by Northerners." To properly implement the federal character principle, a bill was sent to the Nigerian National Assembly for amendment to enable FCC effectively enforce the principles of equity and fairness, and also enable public officers to comply with rules and regulations issued by the commission" (Nzeshi, 2012). The implication of the request to amend the FCC act shows that the principle and the structure put in place to enforce its implementation is not totally effective as envisaged by the government, and this is amply corroborated by Nzeshi (2012) submission that "the inefficiency of the FCC to effectively enforce its mandate as a government watchdog in identifying and addressing inequality is increasingly worrisome." Meanwhile the current chairman of the Federal Character Commission (FCC) in Nigeria is Dr. Muheeba Farida Dankaka (OON). She was appointed as the Executive Chairman of the FCC by President Muhammadu Buhari on April 28, 2020. She still occupies the position till date-September,2024.

In the same vein, Ekeh (1989) contends that "its most radical and damaging application has been in the bureaucracies and public services of the federation. As permanent secretaries have been kicked around, removed and sometimes dismissed." He observed further that the application of the FC principle "has invaded the integrity and standards of public bureaucracy and other governmental bodies that normally require safeguards from the ravages of politics. "Furthermore, the negative effects of federal character on the public sector performance in Nigeria can be gleaned from the work of Forrest (1993), where he argues that the implementation of the principle of federal character in the public service "not only led to poor appointments but also enhanced mediocrity rather than merit." To promote administrative effectiveness for performance in the Nigerian

public service, Utomi (2005) observed that "we need to engage on the issues of competence, commitment, conflict of interest and career certainty. From there come both threats to the effectiveness of the civil service and opportunities for the service to be the anchor of a Nigerian renaissance.

The contributions of a foremost scholar and practitioner in Nigerian public administration, Adamolekun (2008) to this discourse were more probing, when he asserts thus: *"Has the federal character (FC) principle promoted or retarded national loyalty and stability? Or has the area or ethnic region of a person become the key factor in determining his quality as an individual?"* He argues further that "only a critical assessment of years of implementing the FC principle, would help determine the desirable way forward." It is quite relieving that he answered the above questions in a related discussion thus: The "federal character" principle that was introduced as Nigeria's path to achieving "representative bureaucracy" was morphed into the bad practice of politicization. Capacity development programmes for public servants that were a major concern during the immediate pre and post-independence years was progressively neglected notwithstanding the strong case made for it in the Udoji report 1974 (Adamolekun, 2007).

It is very clear from the above submission, why administrative effectiveness in the Nigerian public service for sustainable development may continue to be a mirage. Contributing to the debate on public sector ineffectiveness, Suleiman (2009) contends that "poor capacity of the majority of civil servants, sometimes to the point of illiteracy" arising from the application of the FC is one of the reasons for poor performance of the Nigerian public service. The views of Suleiman (2009) and Adamolekun (2009) goes to support the argument that the neglect of capacity development programmes for public servants and the implementation of the FC offer a credible explanation on the ineffectiveness of the Nigerian public

bureaucracy for sustainable development in Nigeria. Also, Tonwe and Oghator (2009) submit that “federal character allows ethno-regional patrons and their clients to exploit and mismanage state resources without contributing to any meaningful development.” As noted by Ojo (2009), “there is no greater inequality than the equal treatment of unequal.” The FC policy as practiced in Nigeria is elitist and class biased, additionally, it leads to a blurring of the boundary between the pursuits of meritocracy and ethnic balancing, thereby creating inadvertently a multiple system of citizenship in the polity.

In addition, the principle and its application have brought about the unintended effect of creating situations of 'elimination by substitution' which makes it counter-productive. This it does through discrimination in appointment and promotion. The principle attempts to achieve equality of all states, whereas states are not equal in population, and size of the pool of candidates for appointment (Ojo, 2009; Tonwe and Oghator, 2009).

According to Ayoade (2009), equality of states in the implementation of the FC principle as enshrined in the Nigerian constitution means "that the North was represented in the ratio 19:17 (52.8 percent) of public posts." He posits that "this situation is further complicated by the fact that arithmetical justice does not necessarily translate to socio-political justice. A representative bureaucracy does not necessarily translate into power equality for the members” (cited in Ojo, 2009: v). Every administration has its own policy goals (Oaikhena,2023).

Viewed from the foregoing submissions, the federal character principle presents an ambiguous and deceitful recipe for equity and unity in a federal society like Nigeria. Supporting the importance of merit as strategy for manpower procurement in the nation's quest for administrative effectiveness and enhanced performance for sustainable development. Soludo (2012) argued that the emergence of a merit driven culture is, therefore, a key outcome of Vision 20:20:20 and an area of immediate policy

focus. To this end, a comprehensive review of ethnic balancing measures and diversity management related laws such as the implementation of the federal character principle will be undertaken with a view to ensuring greater promotion of merit for sustainable development in Nigeria.

According to The Transformation Agenda (2011-2015), Nigeria's inability to attain sustainable development in the past has been attributed to the nation's inability to tackle development challenges such as poverty, unemployment, corruption and security hinged on bad governance and ineffective institutions/agencies of government. The poor implementation of the principle of federal character in the Nigerian public service is therefore capable of bringing into the service incompetent workforce that lacks the ability to implement the policies of government for sustainable development. Gberevbie (2010) however argued that predicating employee recruitment on federal character does not mean that such an employee cannot contribute meaningfully towards the enhancement of the goals of the organization. This is particularly so where appropriate recruitment strategies involving the screening of potential employees based on relevant skills, experience and educational qualifications are adopted. What is important therefore is the ability of the individual employed and his/her willingness to work for the organization. In addition, through proper staff training and development by organizations of their workforce, organizational productivity is enhanced even where incompetent employees would have been employed through inappropriate recruitment strategies.

In the same vein, Olaopa (2012) commends the federal character principle as one of the "effective nation-building strategies invented for managing the combustible diversity in Nigeria." He however argues that "this principle has badly eroded professional and competency capacity of the public service." With this state of affairs, how can Nigeria attain

sustainable development? Olaopa (2012) responded to this poser by alluding to the declining content of the nation's tertiary education without the right skill to fill in the capacity gap in the public service. He concluded that "the nation unfortunately, could also no longer benefit from a "town and gown" networking that harnesses and deploys the full weight of the available academic capital and capacities to the task of national development" (Olaopa, 2012). In this regard, the application of the FC principle has failed to offer credible solutions to administrative ineffectiveness in the Nigerian public service and has actually become a drag on sustainable development. The implication of the foregoing is that unethical behavior among public officials and low productivity in the Nigerian public service can be explained by the appointment of incompetent personnel through the application the FC principle that makes it possible for people from the different segments of the society to be represented in government without due consideration for merit and quality training to enhance productivity.

Poor performance of officials in the Nigerian public service

One of the manifestations of the implementation of the federal character principle is the poor employee procurement practice, which results in unethical behaviour among public sector workers in Nigeria. Below are some of the instances: The audit investigation ordered by the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Petroleum Resources towards the end of 2011, with the involvement of Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), and was carried out by an internationally recognized audit firm- KPMG, revealed that the cost of subsidy payment on petroleum products not consumed by end users due to losses from theft and even those not supplied for use in Nigeria between 2007 and 2009 amounted to NGN11.8 billion or USD76.13million (Agbo,2012).

In the month of March 2012, the Nigerian Senate set up an Ad hoc Committee to investigate unethical behaviour amongst public officials in the Nigerian Police Pension Fund Administration. While testifying on the pension fund management to the Senate Adhoc Committee, the former Head of Service of the Nigerian Civil Service and Chairman of the Nigerian Public Service Reform Committee of 2012, Stephen Oronsaye revealed that “top government officials were known to have falsified documents in order to siphon money from the pension fund” (Onwukwe, 2012). He disclosed that during his tenure as Head of the Nigerian Civil Service, it was discovered that the fraud was perpetrated from the office of the Accountant General of the Federation. According to him, "The Federal Government of Nigeria spent NGN5 billion or USD32.26 million monthly as pension when in the actual sense, pension expenses ought to be NGN1 billion or USD6.5 million only” (Onwukwe, 2012).

Furthermore, the Director, Pension Administration in the Office of the Head of Service, Dr. Sani Shuaibu and 31 other top officials were arrested by the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) for theft of NGN4.5 billion or USD29.03 million belonging to the Nigerian Police Pension Fund (Abuh, & Musari, 2012; Adewole, 2012). The Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) is a governmental agency established to oversee all port matters in Nigeria as it relates to international trade. However, appointment of public officials based on federal character principle/political patronage led to the appointment of Chief Bode George, a former National Vice-Chairman (West) of the ruling party in Nigeria- People's Democratic Party (PDP) as Chairman, board of the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) in 2009. Chief Bode George and four other board members were charged by the EFCC before a Lagos High Court and were eventually jailed for contract inflation and mismanagement of NGN100 billion or USD645.16 million belonging to the NPA (Fanoro,

2012). This is a case of unethical behaviour amongst public officials to rob the nation of the benefits of international trade and development. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2022) posit that “morality is the health of a society, and a society plagued with immorality is a sick society”. It is unfortunate that the funds that would have gone into developmental drive of the government are being mismanaged by incompetent workforce arising from the application of federal character principle in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study was centered on the theory of Liberalism by John Locke, which emphasizes on equal rights, individual freedom and equal opportunities for all citizens. Thus, the Nigerian public service must operate as an entity promoting equality and fairness at all times. Every citizen must therefore enjoy fair treatment despite their status or tribe, the opportunities in the decision making, appointment or recruitment must not be equally distributed to enhance development and peace. This condition or situation is what the federal character principle is trying to address (equity and fairness to all parts or geographical divides of the country).

Summary

The study examines the challenges and impact of the federal character (FC) principle in Nigeria. It observed that the FC principle as practiced in Nigeria diverts emphasis from merit (based on hard work and achievement) to sharing privileges and benefits accruable from representative bureaucracy, it thus limits effectiveness in public bureaucracy and ultimately national development. The application of FC principle runs counters some features of the Weberian bureaucratic model of rationality in the procurement and promotion of employees as cardinal planks

upon which formal organizations should be built. This state of affairs impacts on administrative effectiveness and the expected role of public bureaucracies in policy implementation for sustainable development.

The study observes that the practice of the Federal Character principle in Nigeria suffers from a major contradiction, because it brings about division amongst Nigerians rather than foster unity as was originally intended by its proponents as a policy option for managing the challenge of equal representation of people from different parts of the society in a multi-ethnic state like Nigeria. It submitted that where appropriate recruitment strategies involving the screening of potential employees based on relevant skills, experience and educational qualifications are adopted and the proper staff training and development of the workforce, organizational productivity could be enhanced even where incompetent employees would have been employed through (in some instances), the poor application of federal character principle in the Nigerian public service.

Finally, it was discovered that despite the efforts of the government to ensure equity and fairness, federal character principle has not achieved the desired results due to poor implementation in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The federal character principle, aimed at promoting national unity and balancing, has faced challenges in its implementation, leading to inefficiencies in the public sector. The study concludes that there is a need for restructuring of federalism in Nigeria, prioritizing merit in recruitment and promotion, and emphasizing human capacity and institutional development. It also concludes that building national consciousness and fundamentally changing the nature and character of leading elites and policy products are also crucial for effective public

sector management. Based on this conclusion, it is therefore recommended that:

1. Federal government should prioritize merit in recruitment and promotion, ensuring geo-political balancing without compromising competence, to enhance the effectiveness of the public sector.
2. The Nigerian public sector should emphasize human capacity and institutional development, and promote good governance devoid of sentiments and unethical behaviour, to improve service delivery and performance.
3. Policy makers should fundamentally change the nature and character of leadership and policy products, shifting from particularistic tendencies and interests to a more nationalistic and inclusive approach, to drive development and national unity.

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THE GROWING AWARENESS OF THE ROLES OF COMMUNITY POLICING IN ESAN LAND, EDO STATE, NIGERIA

Aziegbemhin S. IKHAYERE, Ph.D

Department of Public Administration

College of Management and Social Sciences (COLMASS)

Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria

ikhayereaz@gmail.com

08053330493; 08035746112

Abstract

This study empirically examined the roles of community policing on crime prevention in Nigeria. It specifically aimed at investigating the extent of awareness of community policing in Esan land. To achieve this, an online survey method of investigation was applied as well as structured questionnaire were distributed in the major communities in Esan West Local Government Area, of Edo State. A sample size of 201 respondents was carefully selected through random sampling techniques. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 20.0) was used for all the analyses. All tests were carried out at the 5% level of statistical significance. The findings revealed that greater number of respondents are aware of community policing in their locality. It also revealed that there is a significant relationship between crime prevention and community participation in sensitization of crime prevention. It recommended that there is need to improve management practices in community policing; and the changes management required

should be clearly recognised for the sake of forging community policing partnerships and implementing problem-solving strategies which will necessitate changes in the organisational structure of policing.

Key Words: Community policing, crime prevention, vigilante services and insecurity.

Background to the study

Community policing in Nigeria is a security tactics used as an alternative or complementary effort from the immediate community to support the efforts of police force in fighting crime and criminal activities. As a matter of fact, the police in Nigeria cannot sustain or maintain crime free communities devoid of voluntary local efforts to complement theirs. It is also believed that the people residing in a particular community can effortlessly recognise those people perpetrating evil in their immediate environment and will be easy for them in tracking them down; they have sufficient knowledge of geographical settings of their areas (Olusegun, 2016).

Community policing in Nigeria takes different forms ranging from Community Development Association (CDA); Peace and Security Committee; Landlords and Tenants Security Harmony in which certain able-bodied men in the community are grouped to watch over the community rotationally; Civilian Joint Task Force (in the northern region); Vigilante Service Group and so on (Olusegun, 2016).

In all societies, it is the responsibility of law enforcement agencies and the police in particular to keep law and order, as this is the main purpose for which they are recruited and trained. They are mainly saddled with the obligations of preventing crime and apprehending criminals (Mulugeta & Mekuriaw, 2017). In performing their duties of crime prevention, the police are faced by certain difficulties such as the perception of the public of the police being non-committed and irresponsible, thus affecting their

relationship negatively (Kasali & Odetola, 2016). Solving a crime requires the involvement of the community, without which it will be difficult for the police to successfully prevent or solve problems of crime. Given these challenges, the introduction of community policing became the best alternative to prevent crime or to reduce the rate of same. The justification behind this joint work is the belief that the police alone cannot ensure and maintain security in a community, and in this regard, the concept of community policing was developed (Mulugeta et al, 2017).

Most recently security has been redefined following the awareness by government that security cannot be monopolised locally as well as globally. This consciousness has led to broadening the idea of security to incorporate private participants and civilians in the management of security (Kasali & et al, 2016). Effective community policing is only possible with a level of trust between the police and the community. But, in Nigeria, there is a feeling of distrust between the public and the police, which makes the concept of community policing unrealistic and unachievable. This mistrust stems from the inability of the police to share power with the civilians as they are used to receiving orders from their superiors, as well as the fact that they find it hard to accept another policing model different from the traditional model they have been used to for a very long time (Gbenemene & Adishi, 2017). In view of this, the study examines the roles of community policing on crime prevention in Nigeria, with the study area of Esan land, made up of five Local Government Areas in central senatorial district of Edo State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The palpable tension as a result of insecurity has affected the dignity and quality of life of both individuals and the society. This has portend danger for peace, progress and development of the country. The citizens need peaceful and safe environment to be able to attain their social, economic and political dreams. The